

IMPACT OF EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION IN DECISION-MAKING ON THE COMMITMENT OF BANK EMPLOYEES IN OGBOMOSO METROPOLIS

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between employee participation in decision making and organizational commitment in commercial banks within Ogbomoso Metropolis. The study adopted a survey research design. Respondents' age range was between eighteen (18) to fifty-five (55) years. Data were obtained with 150 questionnaires administered to employees of Commercial Banks in Ogbomoso Metropolis, using simple random sampling technique. The data were analyzed using Pearson's Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis.

The result revealed that there is correlation between employee participation and organization commitment. The correlation resulted in $p < .01$ which showed a significant relationship between employee participation and organization commitment at 1 percent level, it also indicated that the higher the level of employee participation in decision making, the higher will be the organization commitment. Results revealed relationship between employee participation in decision making explain 74.2% variation in organizational commitment using commercial banks in Ogbomosho. Regression model is also significant. Delegative participation has a direct, positive and significant impact on organizational commitment. Consultative participation has a direct, positive and significant impact on organizational commitment and representative participation has a direct, positive and significant impact on organizational commitment. This also validated our hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between employee participation in decision making and organization commitment. The standardized coefficients (Beta) value revealed that the independent variable is statistically significant at 0.05 significant level.

The study concluded that there is a positive relationship between employee participation in decision making and organizational commitment and recommended that employees must be encouraged to participate in decision making process at various levels of the organization and be provided with required skills and information to enhance an informed decision.

Keywords: Employee, Participation, Decision making, Organizational commitment.

Introduction

Economic globalization advent comes with both opportunities and challenges. In today's competitive world, every organization is faced with new challenges as regard sustained productivity and creating committed workforce. It is thereby imperative to deal with organization commitment in the auspice of employee participation and others as concerned in decision making (Chukwuemeka, 2020). Nowadays, hardly can any organization perform at its peak unless each employee is committed to the organization's objectives. Undisputedly, it is important to understand the concept of commitment and its feasible outcome as it relates with employee's participation in organization decision making. Organizational commitment is

important to researchers and organizations because of the desire to retain a strong workforce. Researchers and practitioners are keenly interested in understanding the factors that influence an individual's decision to stay or leave an organization (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2021).

Decision is the action of deciding a conclusion reached and a judgment arrived at (Dede, 2019). Therefore, decision-making is the most germane activity of management of multifarious organization ranging from small-scale organization to multinational corporations. Decisionmaking styles throughout organizations are changing because the task, the environment and the people have changed. We are no longer marching troops into battle; we do not want blind obedience. Competitive advantages are now the result of employee making decision thinking being creative and asking questions. When most managers are honest, they will acknowledge that their employee often have greater knowledge about the work than they do. Clearly, effectiveness can only be achieved with their total involvement management at time, see decision to the heart of their job in that, they must always choose what is to be done who will do it where and most at time how it will be done (Irawanto, 2015; Khattak, Igbal. & Bashir, 2012).

Organizational commitment is a complex and challenging concept in management and organizational behavior. Meyer and Allen's three-component model, which includes affective commitment (emotional attachment), continuance commitment (accumulation of valued side bets), and normative commitment (motivation to conform to social norms), has been the dominant framework (Nwana, Abomeh, Okafor & Mba 2019; Suta, 2023). Employee Participation in Decision-making (PDM) is crucial for promoting employee performance. Employees feel empowered and able to express their opinions, leading to increased performance. PDM is a multidimensional construct, involving various types of people and their involvement levels. Encouraging participation in planning, target setting, and evaluating results can enhance employee performance. It is based on the above that this paper wishes to explore the relationship between employee participation in decision making and organizational commitment using commercial banks in Ogbomoso.

Statement of Research Problem

Employers often baffle when their highly-rated employees under-perform and at attrition, resign and leave the organization. They fail to understand why some employees are not committed to the organization even though they have proactively implemented fair compensation policies and Human Resource (HR) practices to motivate and retain them. It can be costly if employees are not committed in their jobs, and if they lack the motivation to exercise their full potentials. Furthermore, employees unending search for fulfilment, recognition and job satisfaction has necessitated change of job in search for an employment that will meet their overall goal. Therefore, this research is conducted to better understand the two major concept, Employee participation and Employee commitment, the related variables and outcomes in Ogbomoso environment. The research area is restricted to the employees of all commercial banks in Ogbomoso, Oyo State due to constraint of resources and scale of survey. The present work seeks to contribute some useful proposition adaptable for the management of commercial banks both in Ogbomoso, Oyo State and anywhere else the context is being needed.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to explore the relationship between employee participation in decision making and organizational commitment with a particular focus on commercial banks in Ogbomosho case.

Specifically, the study seeks to;

- i) ascertain the nexus between delegative participation and organizational commitment.
- ii) evaluate relationship between consultative participation and organizational commitment.
- iii) assess the connection between representative participation and organizational commitment.
- iv) explore whether delegative participation, consultative participation and representative participation jointly and independently predict organizational commitment.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are considered;

H₀₁: There is a significant relationship between delegative participation and organizational commitment.

H₀₂: There is a significant relationship between consultative participation and organizational commitment.

H₀₃: There is a significant relationship between Representative participation and organizational commitment.

H₀₄: Delegative participation, consultative participation and representative participation can jointly and independently predict organizational commitment.

Literature Review Employee Participation

Participative management is a tool that is used to motivate the employees. When subordinates are involved in decision-making at all levels it is known as participation. According to New-storm and Davis, participation is the mental and emotional involvement of people in group situations that encourages them to contribute to group goals and share responsibility for them. Employee participation involves management actively encouraging staff to assist in running and improving business processes and operations (Nwanah et.al, 2019).

When an employee participates in a business activity, it means he shares the activity with others. These others form one team with the employee and the team is responsible for completion of a goal or project. The team provides the forum where the employee can suggest ideas to make the item more efficiently and make decisions about his portion of the team's project. Whether the level of the employees' involvement is major or minor, all team members are encouraged to participate.

Employee participation involves management actively encouraging staff to assist in running and improving business processes and operations. Also known as employee involvement, employee participation includes management recognizing individual employees' opinions and input, so that employees understand that management views them as unique and individually valuable to running the business. Employee participation in management can vary depending on the level of management. There are five levels of participation: information, consultative, associative, administrative, and decisive. Information participation allows employees to express their views on economic matters. Consultative participation involves employees acting as consultants for safety, health, and welfare, with management making decisions.

Associative participation involves employees morally agreeing with management's opinions. Administrative participation involves employees participating in managerial functions and selecting the best decisions for implementation. Decisive participation involves employees and management working together on welfare and production issues.

Forms of Participation in Decision Making

Cotton et al. (2010) identified six forms of participation in decision-making which are:

Employee Ownership: Employee ownership is a formal method of involving employees in decision-making, often through equity shares. It serves as both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Klein (2010) proposed three models of psychological effects of employee ownership: intrinsic satisfaction, instrumental satisfaction, and intrinsic satisfaction. Chukwuemeka (2020) found a significant relationship between employee commitment and participation in decision-making, with positive job attitudes being a key factor.

Consultative Participation: Consultative participation in decision-making is facilitated by quality circles, a group of employees from various levels of a company. These circles meet regularly to discuss ways to improve quality and resolve production issues. A study found that 90% of Usacorp and 76% of Ukayco employees felt quality circles provided greater participation in their work. Toyota claims quality circles help maintain an edge over competitors, fostering creativity and innovation. Consultative participation positively impacts an organization's success through job satisfaction, commitment, and productivity.

Informal Participation: Informal participation occurs through interpersonal relationships between lower management, allowing employees to indirectly contribute to decisions. Strong supervisor-employee relationships directly affect job satisfaction, improving organizational efficiency. High-quality supervisor-employee relationships result in increased participation, influenced by trust between supervisor and subordinates. Bhatti, et.al, (2010) indicate that trust can play a huge role in satisfaction of employees and that the type of work environment determines whether or not trust will be expected to result in a positive outcome. He noted that high levels of trust results in more positive attitudes, higher levels of cooperation and superior levels of performance which shows trust within an organization result in positive work ethics and productivity.

Short-term Participation: this is seen as an informal participation which mostly consist of rare events in which an employee can participate. According to Steinheider *et al.* (2006) though shortterm participation is not widely used, it shows positive results with satisfaction which will enhance a positive impact on productivity.

Participation in Work Decisions: It is the form of participation where employees have a high influence on the decisions made. It involves formal and direct means where employees participate in decisions concerning the organization directly. White and Ruh's 1981 survey of 2775 employees in six Midwest manufacturing plants found a positive correlation between employee participation and job attitudes. This indicates that employees are more involved and motivated, leading to higher positive impacts on the organization. Most researchers found a positive correlation between these forms of participation.

Benefits of Promoting Employee Participation

Stronger workplace Community: When everyone participates, the company is benefitted by the development of an employee community. Employees that feel their opinion is valued and see changes designed to benefit both them and the customer are more likely to feel invested in the success of the company. These employees want to share their opinions on how to improve because the quality of their work environment and the product matter to them.

Improved Communication: Another big benefit of employee participation is the breaking down of traditional communication barriers. Employees that have a solid avenue for speaking their thoughts and fears regarding the company direction are more likely to point out trouble points in a workflow or innovative new ways of doing things.

Stress Reduction: Participation can also serve to reduce stress in both employees and employers. Stress can build up over uncertainties regarding company changes, because of new workflows, or because employee ideas are not taken into consideration. If allowed to build up over time for too long, stress can have a number of significant impacts on the body such as elevated blood pressure, headaches, or lack of motivation (Khan, et.al, 2011). All of which can cause employees to miss more work and to not be as productive while they are working.

Boosting Productivity: employee participation in decision making can also help to make them more productive in the long run. This occurs for a couple of reasons including less stress, a happier work environment, feeling valued, and a commitment to see positive changes to their fruition. In addition, some of the changes or workflows suggested by employees might actually improve processing time or make certain aspects of the job much faster.

Increased Product Quality: Employee engagement can also play itself out in a way that makes the final product produced by your company much better. For instance, if employees are better informed on the direction of the company, they will be able to better communicate these ideas to customers. Or, if employee suggestions are taken into consideration, new workflows will be implemented faster to increase product output.

Concept of Employee Commitment

Commitment is a force that binds individuals to a course of action relevant to one or more targets. It is reflected in the attitudes and behaviors of employer delegates, and employers can be better or worse than their representatives. High levels of commitment can lead to favorable organizational outcomes, as it reflects the extent to which employees identify with the organization and are committed to its goals. Research has shown that organizational commitment has a positive correlation with job performance, job satisfaction, and morale. However, low commitment can also be associated with low levels of morale and hinder the organization's ability to recruit highquality employees (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2021). Employee commitment can take different forms, making it difficult to define as an HR variable. The context, direction, and development of commitment, as well as the extent to which commitment influences behavior, can result in confusion and debate.

Component Model of Commitment

Allen & Meyer (1990) developed an early model that has received considerable attention. The three components model they advocated was based on their observation that existing definitions of commitment at that time reflected at least three distinct themes: an affective emotional attachment towards an organization (Affective Commitment); the recognition of costs associated with leaving an organization (Continuance Commitment); and a moral obligation to remain with an organization (Normative Commitment). Employee commitment is not always linked to superior performance (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2021). Low affective and normative commitment may not yield performance benefits, as leaving the organization is costly. The Three Component Model of Commitment, developed by Meyer and Allen, explains that commitment is a psychological state with three components: affective, continuance, and normative. This model can enhance employee commitment, engagement, well-being, and job satisfaction, ultimately leading to better performance.

Dimensions of Organizational Commitment

Affective commitment: Affective commitment refers to an employee's desire to stay with their organization, identifying with its goals, feeling a sense of fit, and being satisfied with their work. High affective commitment is considered the most important form of commitment, as it has the most potential benefits for organizations. Employees with high affective commitment go beyond duty for the organization's good, demonstrating a strong emotional attachment to their job.

Continuance Commitment: Continuance commitment refers to employees' desire to remain with their organization due to a lack of work alternatives and remuneration. This type of commitment can lead to dissatisfaction and disengagement, as employees may feel the loss of their salary, benefits, and social connections is greater than the benefits they might gain in a new role. This type of commitment is more likely in established, successful roles or those who have received multiple promotions within one organization.

Normative Commitment: This type of commitment occurs when you feel a sense of obligation to your organization, even if you're unhappy in your role, or even if you want to pursue better opportunities. You feel that you should stay with your organization, because it's the right thing to do. This sense of obligation can stem from several factors. You might feel that you should remain with your organization because it has invested money or time in your training. Or perhaps it provided a reward in advance, such as paying for your college tuition. This obligation can also result from your upbringing. For instance, your family might have stressed that you should stay loyal to your organization.

Drivers of Employee Commitment

Bragg (2002) identified three key factors influencing employee commitment: fairness, trust, and supervisors. Fairness involves eliminating feelings, prejudices, and desires to balance conflicting interests. Employers should pay competitive wages, offer unbiased policies, provide competitive benefits, and promote qualified employees. Trust is essential for nurturing commitment, and employers should be

consistent, maintain confidence, and encourage employee involvement. Research shows that commitment to supervisors is more strongly linked to performance than commitment to organizations. High-quality managers are crucial for retaining high-quality employees, and organizations should select, train, evaluate, and reward them for trustworthy behavior. Effective managers inspire loyalty, trust, and admiration, making it essential for organizations to focus on these factors to foster employee commitment.

Forms of Participation with Effect on Organizational Commitment

Employee participation in the workplace can be categorized into delegative, direct, and consultative participation.

Direct Participation: this involves giving decision rights to employees, while representative participation involves giving decision making rights to representatives like worker directors, work councils, and trade unions. Direct participation can be viewed as three dimensions: the employee's voice, the influence of employees over decisions, and providing relevant information. The importance of management-employee consultation lies in the opportunity for employees to learn more about workplace issues and influence their determination (Kim, MacDuffie, & Pil, 2010).). Direct participation should be arranged in strategic planning for various reasons, such as increasing employees' understanding of business strategy, creating ownership, and improving business strategy. However, the importance of employee participation may not always reflect a broad organizational culture, as advanced technologies may undermine individual tasks and emphasize a more integrated system of work (Olowe, Moradeyo & Babalola, 2013).

Delegative Participation: Delegation empowers employees to solve problems and make recommendations to management. It not only distributes power within the organization but also develops their abilities as they carry out delegated duties. Delegative participation can be divided into two sub-forms: individual delegation, where employees are given extended rights and responsibilities to carry out their work without constant reporting back to managers, and group delegation, where groups of employees are given rights and responsibilities to carry out common tasks without regular reporting back to managers (Suta 2023).). Consultative participation can also be divided into individual and group delegations. Both concepts contribute to the overall success of an organization.

Consultative Participation: Consultation is a process where organizations involve employees in decision-making processes, allowing for the exchange of ideas and different perspectives. It is directly related to employee participation, enabling them to reach technically correct decisions. In organizations with autocratic management, consultation is more likely to lead to quality decisions. Consultative participation involves long-term, formal, and direct participation, focusing on job issues. It involves a lesser level of employee authority than delegation participation (Wainaina, Mike Iravo & Waititu, 2014).

There are two forms of consultation: individual consultation, which involves discussions between employees and their managers, and group consultation, which is a group of employees discussing work-related topics at an ongoing basis. Individual consultation can be face-to-face or arm-length, while group consultation can be temporary or permanent. The extent to which consultation leads to quality decisions depends on the amount of relevant information shared among involved parties. Representative

Participation: Representative participation in organizations is a form of employee involvement that can be formal, indirect, or medium to low influence. It can be through joint consultative committees, works councils, or employee members of Boards of Directors or Management. Employees participate through representatives elected to governing councils or on the board of directors, which can have a positive effect on economic performance, particularly in reducing costs and employment in the short term. Representative participation is more effective than direct participation in enhancing employees' organizational commitment and facilitating high trust and low conflict relations among management, workers, and unions (Ugwu, Okoroji & Chukwu, 2019).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for Employee Participation and Organizational Commitment. **Source:** Researcher’s Conceptualization, 2025.

Theoretical Review

Organizational effectiveness is linked to individual effectiveness, and managers must treat employees fairly. Employee involvement in decision-making is crucial for job satisfaction, commitment, and motivation. McFarland (1968) suggests participative decision-making is rooted in company philosophy, managerial style, and organizational climate. Likert and McGregor (1960) recommend participative group management systems with high trust and participation. Both individual and collective efforts are essential for organizational success. This study was of the following theories;

Social Exchange Theory

According to Saks (2006) employee participation is provided by social exchange theory. The theory argues that obligations are generated through employers engaging employees in decision making. According to the theory relationships evolve over time into trusting, royal and mutual commitments as long as parties abide by certain rules of exchange. It involves reciprocity or repayments rules such that the actions of one-party lead to a response or actions by the other party (Armstrong, 2012). According Balain and Sparrow (2009), social exchange theory best describes employee participation because it sees feelings of loyalty,

commitment, discretionary effort as all being forms of reciprocation by employees to a good employer. However, the research extends to social exchange contribution to knowledge by examining how employee participation in decision making.

Olson's Theory

Mancur Olson (1971) argues that large groups of individuals with common interests usually work together to achieve them, as rational, self-interested individuals will not act to achieve their common or group interests unless the number of individuals in a group is small or unless there is coercion or other special device to make individuals act in their common interest. Benefits from most collective goods (CPRs) are collective goods, similar to activities of a nation state, which are available to all members of the organization. Large groups often fail to provide collective goods for their members due to the higher transaction costs of bringing them together. Olson's theory for managing CPRs suggests that if a group is large and heterogeneous, it should be divided into small and homogeneous subgroups, with each subgroup randomly assigned a portion proportionate to the size of the group. Group action can also emerge in less desirable forms such as collusion and oligopolies. Olson also discusses the role of the political entrepreneur in promoting collective action, suggesting that the success of the political entrepreneur will be related to their ability to use selective incentives to motivate participation in collective action.

Buchanan and Tullock's Theory

Buchanan and Tullock's (1962), theory of collective choice is methodologically individualistic, emphasizing the central role of individual behavior in collective actions. They argue that any theory of collective choice must attempt to explain or describe the means through which conflicting interests of individuals are reconciled. Their theory is similar to the theory of private choice in the theory of markets and has much in common with Arthur Bentley's views on collective choice in terms of interplay of group interests. In the context of common pool natural resources (CPNR) management, Buchanan and Tullock's answer is that a group would choose a collective mode of action when each member finds it profitable to act collectively rather than individually. They adopt a "cost" approach, focusing on reducing external costs imposed on individuals by private or voluntary actions. Their theory can explain successes in CPR management where large groups are involved and helps identify external costs that can be reduced through appropriate interventions.

The Theory of Margin

McClusky's (1970), theory of participative behaviour, known as the theory of margin, explains the lack of participation in development activities in the Third World. The higher the margin between load and power, the lesser participation. Lupanga's hypothesis suggests that rural people have heavy load and little power, leading to a lower participation rate. However, this hypothesis cannot explain why people who do not participate in some activities participate in others. Factors affecting participation include expected returns and costs, attitudes, values, skills, project design, and legal, political, and institutional environment. Singh summarizes the theories of Olson, Buchanan, and Tullock, stating that people participate in collective action

when they are organized in small groups, when the expected private benefits exceed the costs, and when there is assurance of benefits accruing to participants.

Empirical Review

Febriansyah, (2010) suggest that allocating decision making to entire work group produces higher acceptance of decisions and a higher chance that the decisions will be implemented efficiently the point to be made is that people affected should participate at the very inception of any plans to introduce change as systematized an existing situation. Failure to do so will only imperil success indeed the concurrence of work people is required so as to increase a more committed performance on the event of achieving organizational goals.

Employees Participatory in decision-making encourage managers to give employees more decision-making authority in order to increase productivity and job satisfaction. As workers advance through the ranks of the company to participate in decision-making, their engagement has an impact on job satisfaction, efficacy, and loyalty to the company (Owuor, Nyambegera & Wainaina, 2020).

Omar (2012), through a study conducted at The Unilever Manufacturing Company on the influences of suggestive system on employee performance in the manufacturing sector revealed that suggestive systems has a high influence on employee performance. The study findings further revealed that an all round suggestive systems is more effective in influencing employee performance and contributes to positive indicators as increased commitments, loyalty, innovations, creativity, quality, motivation and reduced complaints, stress, grievances and conflicts. The all round suggestive systems increases employee knowledge, skills and abilities and created greater understanding of the processes in an organization.

Nuzhath (2014) studied Employee participation and its impact on their Performance. The researched employed Descriptive Survey Design; the data were sourced through questionnaire which was administered to employees (team leaders) of the BPOs of different companies and service sectors. The findings in different BPOs revealed that an excellent performance of the organization and employer-employee relation depends highly on employee participation in decision making. Based on that, the study conducted stated clearly that there is greater significant link between employee participation in decision making and their performance towards the organization.

According to Ojokuku & Sajuyigbe (2014), a number of specific practices, initiatives, and strategies have been developed to give employees opportunities for involvement in traditional bureaucratic hierarchical organizations. Usually, they were originally introduced individually or in groups, usually in a certain department inside the company. Recently, there has been a greater focus on the need to consider the implementation of participatory processes in a more systemic manner. The most well-liked forms of participation include democratic management, informationsharing forums, cooperative labour management training programs, safety and health committees, high-quality work-life programs, teams for employee participation other than quality circles, total quality management teams, collaborative work structures with various job roles, agreements for profit-and gain-sharing, employee ownership programs, worker participation, and quality circles.

Oyebanji (2018) examined the influence of employees' participation in decision making on organization productivity with particular reference to Ladoke Akintola University of Technology (LAUTECH) Teaching Hospital, Ogbomosho, Oyo State, Nigeria. Purposive random sampling technique was used to select Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Ogbomosto Oyo State, Nigeria, while simple random sampling method was used to select two hundred and five (205) respondents. Data were sourced via a structured questionnaire and frequency, percentage, means, standard deviation and linear regression analysis were employed to analyze the data. Results reveal that both direct participation and representative participation have positive and significant impact on organizational productivity. Furthermore, results indicate that level of employees' participation in decision making in Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Ogbomoso is very low due to unwillingness of management to share decision making with employees. The study therefore concludes that employees' participation in decisions making is an alternative paradigm to organizational productivity.

Methodology

The study explored the relationship between Employee Participation in decision making and Organization Commitment of Bank Employee's in Ogbomosho Metropolis.

The research design adopted for this study were descriptive and survey with samples drawn from employees in the banks. The population of the study were respondents consisting of management staff and selected employees from these banks. A convenience sample of 100 employees from selected banks in Ogbomosho Oyo state were selected randomly to ensure proportionality. Data collection sources were primary data, using questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire measures demographic information in Section A, perceived Employee Participation in Decision Making in section B and Organizational Commitment in Section C. The scales in employee participation in decision making were measured on a five-point Likert scale, while that of organizational commitment are measured on a six-point scale. The study aims to provide valuable insights into the Nigerian banking sector.

Table 1

Variables/Factors	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability
Delegative Participation	6	.863	
Consultative Participation	4	.860	
Representative Participation	4	.848	
Affective Commitment	6	.726	
Continuance Commitment	6	.729	
Normative Commitment	6	.726	
Organizational Commitment	18	.876	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The instruments were revalidated and the Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients showed delegative participation 0.869, consultative participation 0.850, and representative participation 0.842. Organizational performance 0.789 was achieved with a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.868. To ensure reliability and validity, only commercial banks employees were included in the questionnaire. The sample size and plan were carefully maintained to avoid ambiguities and ensure the research had a tolerable error margin of 5%. Hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 were tested using Pearson’s Correlation while Hypothesis 4 was analyzed using Multiple Regression.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the result of the findings as regards to this study. It is all about the research results and findings. All the data collected are summarized in the table and sequentially analyzed with the descriptive, inferential and reliability analysis.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Delegative participation	105	1.3333	5.0000	4.050794	.8861843
consultative participation	105	1.25	5.00	3.8405	.92256
representative participation	105	1.50	5.00	3.6476	.82312
affective commitment	105	2.6667	5.0000	4.357143	.5573080
continuance commitment	105	3.5000	5.0000	4.550794	.3791605
normative commitment	105	2.5000	5.0000	4.073016	.6257149
organizational commitment	105	3.2222	4.8889	4.285185	.3352037
employee participation	105	1.3571	5.0000	3.875510	.8704907
Valid N (listwise)	105				

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

The descriptive statistics showed that continuance commitment has the highest mean of 4.55 with standard deviation 0.38 followed by affection commitment with mean 4.36 and standard deviation 0.56, and the delegative participation with mean 4.05 and standard deviation 0.89 is followed by organization commitment with mean of 4.29 and standard deviation 0.34. this is followed by normative commitment with mean of 4.07 and standard deviation of 0.63. Representative participation has the lowest mean of 3.65

and a standard deviation of 0.82. It shows that compared to representative participation and consultative participation, continuance commitment has more impact on organizational commitment.

Test of Hypotheses Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Delegative Participation and Organizational Commitment

Table 3: Correlation between delegative participation and organizational commitment.

Variable	Pearson R	Sub-variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Pearson R	P	Remark
Delegative participation	.529**	Affective commitment	4.357143	.5573080	105	.607**	.000	Sig.
		Continuance commitment	4.550794	.3791605		.630**	.000	Sig.
		Normative commitment	4.073016	.6257149		.605**	.000	Sig.
Organizational commitment			4.285185	3352037			.000	Sig

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

It is shown in the Table 3 that there is a significant relationship between delegative participation and organizational commitment ($r = .529^{**}$, $N = 105$, $P < .01$). The implication of this is that a 1% change in delegative participation resulted in 52.9% change in organizational commitment. Hence, it could be deduced that delegative participation has a positive, moderate and significant relationship with organizational commitment in the study.

Hypotheses 2

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Consultative Participation and Organizational Commitment.

Table 4: Correlation between consultative participation and organizational commitment

Variable	Pearson R	Sub-variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Pearson R	P	Remark
consultative participation	.524**	Affective commitment	4.357143	.5573080	105	.601**	.003	Sig.
		Continuance commitment	4.550794	.3791605		.634**	.001	Sig.
		Normative commitment	4.073016	.6257149		.626*	.000	Sig.

organizational commitment		4.285185	3352037		.000	Sig.
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Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

It is shown in the Table 4 that there is a significant relationship between consultative participation and organizational commitment ($r = .524^{**}$, $N= 105$, $P < .01$). The implication of this is that a 1% change in consultative participation resulted in 52.4% change in organizational commitment Hence, it could be deduced that consultative participation had a positive, moderate and significant relationship with organizational commitment in the study.

Hypotheses 3. H_{03} : There is no significant relationship between Representative participation and organizational commitment

Table 5: correlation between representative participation and organizational commitment

Variable	Pearson R	Sub-variables of organizational commitment	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Pearson R	P	Remark
Representative participation	.578**	Affective commitment	4.357143	.5573080	105	.648**	.000	Sig.
		Continuance commitment	4.550794	.3791605		.652**	.000	Sig.
		Normative commitment	4.073016	.6257149		.635**	.000	Sig.
organizational commitment			4.285185	3352037		.	.000	Sig.

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

It is shown in the Table 5 that there is a significant relationship between Representative participation and organizational commitment ($r = .578^*$, $N= 105$, $P < .01$). The implication of this is that a 1% change in Representative participation resulted in 57.8% change in organizational commitment. Hence, it could be deduced that Representative participation significantly, positively and moderately correlated with organizational commitment in the study.

Hypothesis 4

H_{04} : Delegative participation, consultative participation and representative participation cannot jointly and independently predict organizational commitment

Table 6: Multiple Regression on the Effects of Delegative, Participation, Consultative Participation and Representative Participation on Organization Commitment.

Variables	F- Ratio	Sig of P	R	R ²	Adj R ²	B	T	P
Delegative participation	23.490	.000	.742	.551	.547	.624	4.814	.000
Consultative participation						.621	3.861	.000
Representative participation						.571	2.936	.004

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

Table 6 showed that the linear combination of Delegative participation, consultative participation and representative participation and organizational commitment was significant. $F = 23.490$; $R = 0.742$, $R^2 = 0.551$, $Adj. R^2 = 0.547$; $P < .01$). The independent/predictor variables jointly accounted for a variation of about 54.7% in organizational commitment. The following shows the various relative contributions and levels of significance of the independent variables: Delegative participation ($\beta = .624$, $P < .01$), Consultative participation ($\beta = .621$, $P < .01$), Representative participation ($\beta = .571$, $P < .01$) respectively. It could be deduced from the results that all the independent variables were statistically significant at 1%. It can be concluded that all the independent variables, (Delegative participation, consultative participation and representative participation) jointly and independently predicted organizational commitment in the study.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study evaluated the relationship between employee participation in decision making and organizational commitment focusing on commercial banks in Ogbomosho metropolis. Descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, multiple regression and Pearson Correlation were employed to analyze the data. The results showed a significant correlation between employee participation and organizational commitment at a 1% level, indicating that higher employee participation leads to greater commitment. The regression model also revealed that delegative participation has a direct, positive, and significant impact on organizational commitment. Consultative participation has a direct, positive, and significant impact on organizational commitment, while representative participation has a direct, positive, and significant impact on organizational commitment.

In conclusion, the study found that employee participation in decision making has a significant relationship with organizational commitment in Ogbomosho Metropolis. All the three measures, delegative participation, consultative participation, and representative participation, were correlated with organizational commitment. The findings suggest that much awareness is needed in the area of employee participation in decision making and organizational commitment using commercial banks in Ogbomosho as a reference point. Employee participation in decision-making significantly increases job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The research supports the idea that participation in decision-making leads to positive results in organizational commitment. In order to achieve this, employees should be given

necessary skills and encouraged to own shares in the organization. Good relationships between supervisors and employees, regular meetings, and a high level of commitment to employees are also crucial. The study recommends that organizations should also provide adequate resources, facilities, and training to employees to foster a sense of ownership and commitment.

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